

ODYSSEE, the new EDF and Framatome Nuclear Code System

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ABSTRACT

ODYSSEE is the new state-of-the-art Nuclear Code System designed and developed by EDF and Framatome since 2018 to replace their current code systems for design, safety and fuel reload studies for PWR reactors and based on new versions of APOLLO2, COCAGNE, THYC codes and coupled with CATHARE3. This paper summarizes and describes the main physical models and methodology choices for industrial computations and software architecture aspects. A separate, dedicated paper describes the validation of ODYSSEE vs measurements and reference codes [1].

Keywords: neutronics, core thermal-hydraulics, nuclear data, computer code, safety evaluation

1. INTRODUCTION

EDF and Framatome decided to develop together a new core calculation codes system, ODYSSEE. Since 2018 and based on previous work on the ANDROMEDE and ARCADIA projects, ODYSSEE has been developed, verified and validated to progressively replace the currently used codes, to perform the next generation safety studies in design and operational scopes. ODYSSEE is based on the neutronics codes CARABAS embedding APOLLO2 for lattice calculations and COCAGNE for core ones, the thermal-hydraulics (TH) codes, THYC, and CATHARE3 as a system code. The ATHENA coupler enables multi-physics coupling between neutronics, system and thermal-hydraulics (CATHARE3-COCAGNE-THYC). ODYSSEE's physical validation is presented in a specific paper submitted to PHYSOR 2026 [1].

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Nuclear Data Library

ODYSSEE uses the CEA (Commissariat à l'Energie Atomique) v5.2.0 nuclear data (ND) library which is a hybrid library based on JEFF-3.1.1 [2] except for 4 nuclei: 238U, 56Fe, 55Mn, 90Zr. The 238U and the 56Fe evaluations were produced by the CEA in collaboration with EDF and Framatome. The 55Mn and the 90Zr respectively come from the JEFF-3.3 and the ENDF/B-VIII.0 libraries. The use of these four nuclei was carefully chosen to improve reactivity and power distribution calculations. The CEA v5.2.0 is provided in a compact binary format suited for the lattice code CARABAS (cf. §2.2) and is based on SHEM 281-energy group [3] neutron cross sections (XS) with or without resonant up-scattering effect. The photo-electric XS are based on the EPDL-97 library on a 94-groups mesh. Fine mesh XS and probability tables are also used for the self-shielding computation. Adjustments on the ND were

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defined to increase the BOL reactivity and reduce the reactivity loss during depletion; they were discussed with CEA and are small compared to the uncertainties.

2.2. Fuel assembly transport code and methodology - CARABAS

Overview. ODYSSEE features the deterministic transport code CARABAS, which is a multi-layered system based on the APOLLO2 v2.8 physical modules (solvers, self-shielding, etc.) by CEA [4]. A user layer provides input and output processing and implements the calculation methodology described hereafter. CARABAS solves the multi-group neutron transport equation on PWR 2D fuel assembly geometries. It generates multi-parametric libraries of homogenized and collapsed nuclear data, for both fuel and reflector regions, which are subsequently used by the core simulation code in the classical two-step methodology. It also enables finer transport calculations on 2D geometries of increasing complexity, from fuel cells to assembly patterns and full-core models, with a detailed reflector modeling.

User interface. CARABAS input features a compact, block-oriented and user-friendly format, typically in a few hundred lines (geometric layout of assembly and core components, material compositions, control rod configurations, operating conditions, etc.) with two interfaces: a keyword file-based file and a Python script. Distribution of state points on HPC clusters is featured to efficiently compute large multi-parametric libraries to cover core operating conditions (several thousand calculations). Advanced users can define, beyond the default options, any desired output energy or spatial mesh, ranging from coarse homogeneous assemblies to fine cell distributions, enabling tailored data extraction. An output format based on HDF is used, well-suited for physical analyses, then converted into a matrix representation enabling fast interpolation in the core code.

Methodology. The calculation of the flux and homogenized XS in CARABAS relies on a series of advanced APOLLO2 models inspired from pre-existing methodologies developed by CEA [5] and Framatome [6]. The complexity of physical modeling is encapsulated in pre-configured sets of options depending on the target, ensuring both ease of use and robust results across a wide range of operating conditions (e.g. spatial meshes and self-shielding options are dynamically generated depending on the fuel and absorber materials). Multi-group XS for key resonant isotopes are processed using a self-shielding model that has been carefully optimized for each isotope and resonance. This includes tailored treatment sequences and geometries, ranging from homogeneous cells to heterogeneous multi-cell configurations and isotope mixing models to treat resonance interferences. The interface current collision probability (CP) method is employed to solve the slowing-down equation leading to accurate but fast self-shielding calculations at every state point. For ordinary XS table production, CARABAS implements an energy-space decoupling strategy to optimize computational efficiency (Fig. 1). The APOLLO2 TDT-MOC (Method of Characteristics) solver module [7] is used to solve the transport equation on a fine spatial mesh, typically comprising several thousand meshes per fuel assembly. This is well-suited for handling complex, unstructured geometries with high spatial fidelity and benefits from advanced acceleration techniques. A first flux solution is obtained using the CP solver over 281 energy groups. This flux is then used as a weighting function to obtain XS at 36 energy groups, which are subsequently used in the MOC solver. A direct transport calculation using the MOC over the full energy mesh is also available for reference calculations. Both flux solutions are subsequently combined to reconstruct a fine-resolution flux in both energy and space. This flux is then used to solve Bateman equation and perform isotopic depletion with an extended isotope chain containing about 170 nuclides. This reconstructed flux is also used to homogenize and condense XS to 2 energy groups and to various homogenized spatial meshes.

Figure 1. Overview of the industrial scheme implemented in CARABAS.

A homogeneous B_1 leakage model is available, using the 281-group flux obtained from the CP solver to compute the critical buckling and diffusion coefficients. CARABAS also includes a comprehensive energy deposition model that accounts for both the kinetic energy loss of neutrons through collisions and the transport of gammas. The resulting deposited energy distribution is used to compute pin power at the core level, leading to accurate prediction of power peak factors. Finally, the adjoint flux is used as a weighting function to compute nuclear data needed by the core code for transients (delayed neutron fraction, inverse velocity, prompt neutron generation time).

2.3. Core code and methodology - COCAGNE

COCAGNE is a 3D core simulation platform for PWR [8], organized in functional layers (Fig. 2):

- Python Interface (external layer): it allows to define a set of models and procedures connected to the other codes of ODYSSEE
- Core Modeling Services (intermediate layer, Python): organizes data and manages dependencies, ensuring consistency and modularity across components for scalable evolution.
- C++ Internal Layer: hosts solvers and physical models, sharing a unified internal data model ensuring performance and integration.

It offers both stand-alone advanced usage and full integration within the ODYSSEE User Environment. It enables the computation of key reactor parameters such as reactivity, power distribution, fuel temperature, and neutron detector responses (in-core and ex-core). It includes a microscopic depletion model to enhance neutron cross-section characterization. Fuel thermal and moderator TH feedbacks are handled via a simplified heat transfer solver and either an axial 1D solver for water properties based on a homogeneous 3-equation model, or the ATHENA coupler interfaced with the 3D, 2-phase core TH code THYC (see §2.4). The latter is preferred for specific conditions where the additional computational cost is justified. These models work both in steady-state and transient/kinetic simulations.

Neutronic Flux Computation. Two steady-state and kinetic solvers are available on cartesian geometries:

- a Simplified P_n (SP_n) solver [9], using a Raviart-Thomas finite element method [10]

Figure 2. Architecture of the functional layers in COCAGNE core code.

- a Discrete Ordinates (S_n) solver [11], with a Diamond Difference spatial scheme, consistent with the SP_n , which therefore can be used for Diffusion Synthetic Acceleration (DSA)

In the ODYSSEE industrial methodology, the SP_n solver (at first order with a diffusion correction term) is employed to solve the two-group diffusion equation. A wide range of computations is supported, including direct and adjoint eigenvalue problems, source-driven simulations, and perturbation analyses using SPT or GPT methods. All these computations rely on iterative procedures, with the inverse power method used to converge the fission source and flux distribution. Chebyshev acceleration is applied to enhance convergence speed. The stopping criteria are carefully designed to account for the spectral radius of the iterative algorithm, preventing false convergence — where the difference between successive iterates may appear small, yet the solution remains significantly distant from the true converged state (by several orders of magnitude in algorithmically difficult cases).

Feedbacks and Depletion. The impact of TH and fuel temperature on neutron XS is accounted for through feedback iterations, which are interlaced with the power iterations of the neutronic solver. Isotopic depletion is handled by solving Bateman's equations for approximately 40 actinides and fission products. The integration is performed using adaptive Runge-Kutta methods, specifically the Cash-Karp scheme [12]. To evaluate reaction rates, a second-order Runge-Kutta scheme is employed, allowing significantly larger time steps compared to standard first-order depletion schemes [13].

Homogenization and Equivalence. One of the key advancements in ODYSSEE is the use of heterogeneous XS within fuel assemblies. While full assembly homogenization is generally sufficient for UOX assemblies, more accurate simulations are required for assemblies with stronger heterogeneities — such as burnable absorbers and MOX fuel. Since full pin-by-pin modeling is computationally expensive, an intermediate approach called multi-domain homogenization was developed. With the

proper choice of homogenization geometry (Fig. 3), this method achieves near pin-level accuracy [14] while significantly reducing CPU time. Direct use of CARABAS-generated homogenized XS is insufficient. An equivalence stage is required for consistency with heterogeneous transport solutions. SPH equivalence [15] is applied, and with SP_n solvers, one degree of freedom per energy group remains. This is used to improve interface currents, like with Selengut factors [16,17].

Figure 3 Homogenization options for COCAGNE

De-homogenization. As with any homogenization approach, local quantities such as pin-by-pin power are not directly accessible. A de-homogenization procedure must be used to recover this information. Unlike full assembly homogenization — where the heterogeneous flux shape can be retrieved from the single-assembly CARABAS computation — multi-domain homogenization requires incorporating the flux computed at the multi-domain scale into the factorization process [14].

2.4. Core Thermal-hydraulics code and methodology - THYC

THYC [18] is the reference 3D core TH code of ODYSSEE. It is designed to compute local TH conditions such as pressure, mass flow rate, thermodynamic quality, or density for a given set of boundary conditions at scales ranging from the fuel assembly down to the sub-channel level. THYC allows the simulation of both single and two-phase upward flows along rod bundles at the subchannel scale, which may include spacer grids and nozzles in both steady-state and transient regimes. THYC is mainly used for Critical Heat Flux (CHF) computation as part of PWR safety studies relying on empirical correlations derived from experimental data. Further applications include the determination of CHF penalties in mixed-fuel cores and of precise core power distribution, through the ATHENA coupler, with COCAGNE.

The THYC model is based on 4 transport equations: the 3D compressible conservation equations for mass, momentum and energy for a water-steam homogeneous mixture, as well as a transport equation for the non-equilibrium vapor phase accounting for subcooled nucleate boiling. The equations are discretized using upwind finite volume schemes on staggered grids and are solved using a semi-implicit time-integration involving a predictor-corrector for pressure and momentum. This system of equations is closed by a set of closure laws from the literature, validated against a large database of experimental configurations [1]. These closure laws model the following phenomena: turbulent diffusion, pressure loss (both single-phase and two-phase flow), diffusive heat flux, vapor generation rate, drift velocity and vapor diffusion. Methods have been implemented to reduce THYC CPU time: leveraging core symmetries such as 1/4 or 1/8 (Fig. 4), improving numerical schemes robustness at higher time steps, using state-of-the-art linear solvers, using Anderson acceleration [19], or initializing the core TH conditions using an optimized analytical field. One of the major advances in ODYSSEE is the new Python API PyTHYC. It

allows to initialize the THYC solver from a standard dataset (consisting in fuel assemblies geometries and TH properties, state-points conditions, mesh, closure laws and numeric options) and then dynamically steer the calculation by modifying parameters, fields, and boundary conditions between solver iterations. It also provides a simple way to couple THYC with other solvers, following modern programming standards. PyTHYC is designed for complex studies that require fine-grained, dynamic control over the simulation.

Figure 4. Various levels of computational mesh resolution within THYC.

2.5. Multi-physics coupler - ATHENA

For specific transient computations, the simplified TH solver of COCAGNE can fall short in representing the real core flow configuration. On the other hand, the pointwise neutron kinetic module embedded in CATHARE3 [20] is not precise enough to predict the core power evolution. Thus, to extend the modeling capability of ODYSSEE, a new multi-physics coupling software, ATHENA, was developed. It consists in a Python layer on top of the different codes interfaces that handles data exchange between the codes, execution synchronization as well as overall convergence of the coupled calculation. It relies on open-source SALOME platform's [21] "medcoupling" library to perform field projections and conversions between coupled models. ATHENA provides pre-configured options for the coupling methodology (e.g. data exchange meshes and time schemes) optimized for different types of transients.

3. SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE, USER INTERFACE, AUTOMATION

ODYSSEE software provides an enhanced Python calculation environment called EMC2. It first implements safety calculation procedures/methods, allowing users to focus on physical analysis. This leads to a standardized approach to studies improving quality and maintainability. Second, EMC2 provides two graphical user interfaces (GUI): one for design studies (implementation of advanced methods and exploratory analyses); the other for production studies for operating NPP, focusing on efficient execution. EMC2 also provides a Python command-line interface. These 3 ways of using ODYSSEE are fully equivalent, enabling seamless collaboration between users. A thorough validation of the user input is performed, using a custom data schema. This, combined with the user's context, enables the automatic generation of ergonomic input forms/windows, enhanced with custom-built widgets for operations such as core reloading and rod banks management (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Examples of ODYSSEE Graphical user interfaces with procedures, input panels, core widget

EMC2 wraps the calculation codes, thus standardizing input and output across them and translating physics concepts into code input syntax. The users can easily plug-in new models/solvers without impacting the safety methods. Additionally, EMC2 provides common, shared input and output databases, enabling efficient, shared post-processing tools. Finally, EMC2 manages the execution: each submitted graph is analyzed to check the required CPU resources and time. EMC2 provides smart restart/replay and a reuse feature to skip already executed tasks. A signal-based trigger between tasks, enables downstream tasks to start without waiting for the completion of the upstream ones.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The ODYSSEE nuclear code system, gathering EDF and Framatome expertise, is an advanced simulation tool implementing state-of-the-art methodologies in neutronics (CARABAS-APOLLO2, COCAGNE), thermal-hydraulics (Thermo1D and THYC) and multi-physics couplings (COCAGNE-THYC-CATHARE3 via ATHENA coupler). A specific architecture and a new user environment allow a very detailed modeling of the reactors through a simple, user-oriented interface. ODYSSEE enables accurate and efficient simulation of PWR reactors, addressing complex physical phenomena, to the benefit of reactor design and safety analyses. In conclusion, ODYSSEE brings a significant improvement in the core simulation capabilities and provides a robust tool for the next generation nuclear development.

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